

GENDER AND LANGUAGE POLITENESS

Rosmita Ambarita¹,

Mulyadi²ⁱ

¹STIE Sibolga,

Tapanuli Tengah,

Indonesia

²Fakultas Ilmu Budaya Universitas,

Sumatra Utara,

Indonesia

Abstract:

The aims of this article are to describe gender and language politeness which examines the description of relation of gender and language politeness in the form of speech acts based on gender. The method used in this research is descriptive qualitative. The technique used in collecting data through direct observation, recording, and recording. Determination of the compliance and deviation of the principle of politeness of language is based on indicators of politeness of language derived from Leech's theory. The technique of data analysis in this study is the transcription of data from the records; identify, classify and draw conclusions.

Keywords: gender, language politeness

1. Introduction

Language is a sign system that contains of concept, labels and gender differentiate terms. Language is also very influential on our perceptions and perspectives on something. The language we use every day is seen only as tools of communication, but language is a means of socialization and preservation of an attitude or value. Gender is a concept to identify the differences between men and women in terms of socio-cultural influences. Gender is defined as a mental and cultural interpretation of gender differences between men and women. Gender is usually used to show the division of labor that is considered appropriate for men and women.

Coates's research (2015) shows that in English, the language used by a group of men (hereinafter referred to as a variety of male languages) differs from the language used by a group of women (hereinafter referred to as a variety of female languages). These differences exist in all aspects of language, namely vocabulary, grammar, and

ⁱ Correspondence: email rosa_ambar@yahoo.com

phonology, to the point of using and choosing particles in sentences. In using language, both groups are perceived to display different ways of speaking. These differences tend to discredit the female group in an inferior and subordinate position, while the male group is appointed in a superior and dominant position. The female group is expected to be gentler (lady like) compared to the male group (Lakoff, 1973). Women are seen as more talkative (chatty) and gossiping, speaking more politely, and not swearing, using more adjectives (as a mirror more emotional than rational), and mastering their vocabulary less than men (Coates, 2015).

In society there is often a lack of clarity and misunderstanding about the terms of gender and sex, the two terms actually have different meanings. Nugroho, (2008) argues that gender is the differentiation of the roles of women and men in which social and cultural constructions are formed, so it is not because of the construction that was carried from birth. If "sex" is something that is carried from birth, then "gender" is something that is formed because of an understanding that grows and develops in society. Gender refers to the socio-cultural dimension of a person as male or female. One aspect of gender gives birth to a gender role (general) which is a hope that establishes how women and men should think, behave, and feel.

Coates (2015) made various studies on the influence of the speaker's gender on linguistic variations showing the existence of speeches that are exclusively preferred by women and other speeches that are exclusively preferred by men. For example, in interactions between gender, women generally ask more questions, use more polite speech and cut off less talk than men, and contrary to the myth that women talk more than men, the findings of several studies show that men hear less and talk more than women (Catalan, 2003: 55). This article focuses on the politeness of language and its relation to gender which includes about sex and gender.

2. Review of Literature

2.1 Sex and Gender

The word sex comes from English means gender. In Webster's New World Dictionary, gender is defined as the visible difference between men and women in terms of values and behavior. Gender is a concept used to identify differences between men and women in terms of socio-cultural influences. Gender is defined as a mental and cultural interpretation of gender differences between men and women. Gender is usually used to show the division of labor that is considered appropriate for men and women. There are several language differences between men and women, including phonology, morphology, and diction. In terms of phonology, between men and women have some differences, as in America women use palatal velar not aspirate, such as the words *kjatsa* (spoken by women) and *djatsa* (spoken by men). In Scotland, most women use the consonant / t / in the words *got*, *not*, *water*, and so on. Meanwhile, men more often change consonants / t / with conspicuous glottal consonants. In the field of morphology, Lakoff states that women often use words for color, such as *mauve*, *beige*, *aquamarine*, and *lavender* which are rarely used by men. In addition, women also often use

adjectives such as adorable, charming, divine, lovely, and sweet. Judging from the diction, women have certain vocabulary to show certain effects on them, words and expressions such as; so good, adorable, darling, and fantastic. Besides that, English makes differences in certain words based on gender such as actor-actress, waiter-waitress, Mr.-Mrs. This happens because of public awareness that differences in vocabulary choices are made, illustrating the respective roles held by men and women.

In terms of calling women are also different from men. Usually in calling them (women) words are often used like dear, miss, lady or even babe (baby). In socializing, usually men more often talk about sports, business, politics, formal material, or taxes. Meanwhile, the topic discussed by women leads more to the problems of social life, books, food, drinks, and lifestyle. Women are expected to be more polite when speaking. It can't be imagined a woman uses the word swear "hard", for example damn or shit, women will only say oh dear and so on. By using polite or standard language, women try to protect their wants or needs. In this case, women demand more social status. Gender is a distinction of universal behavior in vernacular cultures. The concept of gender distinguishes time, place, equipment, tasks, gestures, forms of speech, and various perceptions between those associated with men and those associated with women (Budiman, 2004).

Gender is the foundation for the continuity of a community's institutions; self-perception of men and women, what and who they are, allocation of jobs provided, division of authority and patterned through a gender social system. Gender regulation is also standardized through various existing institutions, which are places for socialization and internalization of values such as family, formal education, religion, political system, economic system (Fakih, 1997: 25).

Since childhood, we have learned language through language acquisition we get from the family environment. Through the family environment we are taught from the start of sounds, words and even simple sentences that are not yet perfect, and then we can learn little by little. The language written or memorized must have meaning. Through language we can express ideas or ideas that we think about. Language is the basis of all activities that we do, because language can be said to support all our activities in social life. Language is also used as a means of communication, delivery of information and exchanging thoughts. When we use language as a communication tool, we already have certain goals to be achieved in a communication that has been adjusted and planned in advance, not infrequently the communication just happens spontaneously. What is certain when we do communication, we want so that what we say can be understood by others.

In the use of language, the relationship between language, vocabulary and gender of the speaker can be reviewed sociolinguistically because it involves social problems, namely society and linguistics, namely language. Gender influences language in a society anywhere in the world. Gender is the difference and function of social roles constructed by society, as well as the responsibilities of men and women. Gender is related to the belief process of how men and women should act and act in accordance with structured values, social and cultural provisions where they are.

Women and men have different characteristics and different abilities. The difference in verbal abilities is often caused by the motion factors of limbs, facial expressions, voice and intonation. The difference in language does not mean that two languages are completely different and separate, but their languages are still one, only in the use of male and female languages have different characteristics. Women are more likely to maintain language while men are innovative and renewable. Most of us can distinguish between male and female voices even though they have to be blindfolded, this is because in general it can be said that male voice volume is relatively greater than that of women. Even in the world of sound art, there are groups that distinguish between male and female voices. In women for example there are alto and soprano sounds, while in men there are tenor and bass sounds. This all happens because it deals with the organs of the body that produce sounds that are more or less different in men and women, unfortunately in this paper the author does not discuss in detail about the organs of the body producing the sound.

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2.2 Politeness in Language

According to Leech (1983), politeness is interpreted as a treatment that can reduce shifts in an interaction. The use of language must be subtle, polite civilized, gentle treatment, and virtuous in an effort to reduce conflict or shift. According to Ferguson (1986), politeness applies when a contract of conversation is used by speakers and listeners as an effort to perpetuate harmony communication without causing conflict. Politeness does not refer to politeness solely in language but also refers to nonverbal aspects such as behavior, facial expressions, and tone of voice. Fraser and Nolan (1981) argued that politeness is valid if a contract of conversation used by the speaker and listener intended to perpetuate a harmonious relationship in communication. Brown and Levinson (1987) consider politeness as an attempt to reduce the Face Threat Actions (TAM) in conversations with listeners. In the context of language politeness, Omar (2000) links it with the use of everyday language that does not cause anger, anger and offense from the listener. This will create an atmosphere of harmonious relations between the speaker and the listener.

According to Zamzani, et al. (2010: 2) politeness is behavior that is expressed in a good or ethical way. The politeness of language is reflected in the procedure for communicating through verbal signs or language procedures. The politeness of the language can be done by the way off the speech offender adheres to the principle of language courtesy that applies in the language user community. So, it is expected that speech actors in speaking with their speech partners do not neglect the principle of courtesy. This is to maintain good relations with their speech partners.

3. The Politeness Principles of Geoffrey Leech

A. Maxim of Wisdom

Make the loss of others as small as possible, make the profits of others as big as possible (Leech, 1983: 206). For example, a boss with patience tells his new secretary:

[1] Can you type these letters?

Another more ancient example is the use of the word "may" in the permissive form, but is intended as a command; for example, in a Victorian story about the adventures of a schoolboy, the words a principal uses to his student to send the child away are as follows.

[2] Smith, you may leave now.

At a glance [1] and [2] give the impression that the speaker intends to act politely by giving t the opportunity to do something fun. However, this reasoning cannot be used to explain these two sentences, because [1] will surely be followed by the typing act of the letters, and [2] will also certainly cause the student to leave immediately. It is often felt.

b. Maxim of Generosity

Make yourself as small a profit as possible; make yourself as big a loss as possible. A 'self-centered' philanthropic maxim does not need to be distinguished. For example, the asymmetry contained in sentences [3] and [4] or [5] and [6] can be explained by one of these maxims:

[3] * You can lend your car to me. (impolite)

[4] I can lend you my car.

[5] You must come to dinner at our house.

[6] * We must come and have dinner at your place. (impolite)

(Note: The sign (*) shows that in terms of absolute manners, this speech is less acceptable than the speech of the partner; remember that we are still talking about absolute courtesy, not relative courtesy).

c. Maxim of Praise

Criticize others as little as possible; praise others as much as possible. A praise maxim can be given another bad name, 'Flirt maxim,' but the term 'seduction' is usually used for insincere praise. In this maxim, the negative aspect especially the word "don't" say unpleasant things about other people. Therefore, according to the maxim of praise, a compliment such as "Your cooking is very good" is highly valued, while words like "Your cooking is not tasty at all!" Will not appreciated.

d. Maxim of Modesty

Praise yourself as little as possible; criticize yourself as much as possible. Like the maxims of good manners, the maxim of humility also appears in asymmetrical forms:

[14] A: They are very kind to us.

[14a] B: Yes, that's right.

[15] A: You are very kind to me.

[15a] B: * Yes, that's right.

[16] How stupid I am!

[16a] * How smart I am!

[17] * You are so stupid!

[17a] How clever you are.

[18] Please accept this small gift as a token of our appreciation.

[19] * Receive this great gift as a token of our appreciation.

The sentence [14] shows that it is polite to agree with other people's praise, except if the praise is directed at ourselves. Likewise, sentence [16] shows that self-criticism is considered good, even if for humorous purposes the criticism is exaggerated. In sentence [18], downplaying the meaning of one's own generosity is considered normal and conventional, but this is not the case if this generosity is enlarged exaggerate. It can be seen in [15] and [19] that violating the first sub maxim humility 5 means bragging and constitutes a social offense.

e. Maxim of Sympathy

Reduce the sense of antipathy between yourself and others to the smallest possible; increase sympathy as much as possible between yourself and others. This maxim

explains why congratulations and condolences are polite and respectful acts, even though condolences express the speaker's belief that for the speaker is a negative belief. This is polite when compared to, for example, remarks * I am very happy to hear that your cat is dead, there is still a reluctance to express condolences, because by mentioning the content of propositional X (in condolences), we actually express an impolite belief, that is a belief that is detrimental.

4. Methodology of Research

The method of this research is qualitative descriptive. The data used is in the form of words or sentences. Descriptive research is research that provides research objects based on existing facts. In this case the realization of politeness principles based on gender is described.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Language and Gender

Gender is a concept used to identify differences between men and women in terms of socio-cultural influences. Gender is defined as a mental and cultural interpretation of gender differences between men and women. Gender is usually used to show the division of labor that is considered appropriate for men and women.

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In terms of calling women are also different from men. More often use pronouns for calling them (women) the words that often used like *baby*, *girl*, *girl* or even *baby* (*baby*). In socializing, men usually talk more about sports, business, politics, formal material, or taxes. Meanwhile, the topics more often discussed by women are social issues, books, food, drinks, and lifestyles. Women are expected to be more polite when speaking. It is inconceivable for a woman to use the word swear "hard", for example *damn*, the woman will only see *oh dear* and so on. By using polite or standard language, women try to get their wants or needs. In this case, women need more social status.

Gender also means as roles and responsibilities that are socially conceived of women and men in a particular culture or location supported by the structures of society. Gender can change from time to time, from one community to another, class to

class even from culture to culture. This understanding is in line with the concept of gender according to Budiman as follows: *“gender is a distinctive of universal behavior in vernacular cultures. The concept of gender distinguishes time, place, equipment, tasks, gestures, forms of speech, and various perceptions between those associated with men and those associated with women”*. (Budiman, 2004)

Gender is the basis for the continuation of a social institution. The regulation of Gender also standardized through various existing institutions, which are places for socialization and internalization of values such as family, formal education, religion, political system, economic system (Fakih, 1997: 25).

5.2 The Relation of Gender and Language

The relationship between gender and Language lies on three kinds of relationship according to Graddol and Joan (2003: 13) namely :

- 1) Language reflects gender division;
 - 2) Language creates gender division;
 - 3) Language and social structure influence each other;
- Emotional and intellectual differences between men and women

Male (Maskulin)	Female (Feminin)
- more agresieve	- not too agresive
- not emotional	- more emotional
- independent	- not too independent
- can hide emotion	- hard to hide emotion
- more objective	- more subjective
- not easily influenced	- easily influenced
- more active	- more passive
- straightforward	- home oriented
- rarely cry	- easily touching
- more ambition	- cry more often

5.3 The differences of Language between Men and Women

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5.4 The Relationship between Gender and Politeness of Language

One of the research frameworks of conversational interaction between men and women is politeness theory. This theory suggests that participants in interactions usually "*avoid dealing with threatening actions*" that undermine the social position of the interlocutor. Various alternative definitions of modesty in speech have been put forward. Lakoff (2006), for example, argues that people being polite aims to reduce friction in personal interactions. More recent formulations observe that the degree to which a person is at risk of threatening actions will depend, in part, on one's vulnerability. Thus, the use of politeness might reflect power relations among speakers. Cook-Gumperz argues that politeness does not merely reflect, but also helps produce social relations, stating that it is "*fundamental in generating social order and preparing conditions for human cooperation*".

6. Conclusion

From the description above, it can be concluded that language and gender are related to how gender influences the way we use language and the use of other languages. Areas of language and gender research that can be studied include: differences in language use between men and women, patterns of differences in language use between men and women that can be observed by the public, differences in the way men and women in certain groups, depictions of men and women as communicators in various media, sexist language, public attitudes towards male and female languages, the role of gender differences in changing language use.

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